

Data Collection, Standardisation & Harmonisation

**Cohort Studies in Pandemic Preparedness in the last 5
years: Challenges and Solutions**

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CoMeCT Project
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Why should we care about the standardization or harmonisation of health data?

Why should we care about standardisation?

Semantic and syntactic interoperability of datasets and country-level health data commons is essential for detecting and responding to global health challenges, including emerging infectious diseases, antimicrobial resistance, and vaccine-preventable illnesses.

Standardisation ensures we can put the data together to make inference across studies, populations, variants, etc.

Semantic and syntactic interoperability and high-quality metadata facilitate federated reuse of sensitive data, allowing us to reuse sensitive data without moving or directly accessing the data.

We cannot have pandemic preparedness without data preparedness.

Data understanding precedes data strategy.
Data strategy precedes data investment & data
governance.

Data understanding

What does semantic interoperability look like?

High-dimensional data

[https://doi.org/10.1016/S2589-7500\(23\)00129-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2589-7500(23)00129-2)

<https://public.flourish.studio/visualisation/12613862/>

What does semantic interoperability look like?

Clin-epi data

[https://doi.org/10.1016/S2589-7500\(23\)00129-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2589-7500(23)00129-2)
<https://public.flourish.studio/visualisation/12614209/>

2024 TCB & CCB standards adoption survey

Objective: understand what standards are being used, barriers to standards adoption, how EU can support standards adoption

CoMeCT standards survey responses

33 responses, representing 15 consortia or networks

- 25 responses from CCB, representing 8 consortia
- 4 responses from TCB, representing 3 consortia
- 3 responses from European cohort networks, 1 from multisite RCT external to the TCB/CCB

Data capture or exchange standards used

N=23

Most important barriers to adopting a standard for clinical data capture or exchange

N=24

How the EC can help studies/consortia implement standards for data capture and exchange

N=30

TCB/CCB
recommendations
for supporting the
use of standards

What types of data strategies work best for pandemics?

Data that are not interoperable and do not have metadata

Centralised data sharing approach

Adverse fetal and perinatal outcomes associated with Zika virus infection during pregnancy: an individual participant data meta-analysis

The Zika Virus Individual Participant Data Consortium^a

Summary

Background Zika virus (ZIKV) infection during pregnancy is associated with an increased risk of congenital malformations. The prevalence of short and long-term consequences, however, remains uncertain due to heterogeneity across studies. Individual Participant Data Meta-Analysis (IPD-MA) offers an alternative approach to provide more precise and generalisable estimates through data harmonisation across studies, allowing for standardised definitions and exploration of heterogeneity. This project was undertaken to estimate absolute and relative risks of adverse outcomes for individuals with ZIKV infection during pregnancy.

Methods IPD-MA studies and their datasets were identified through a systematic search conducted in 2018 with the following criteria: observational longitudinal or surveillance-based studies investigating ZIKV during pregnancy or at birth, measured fetal, infant, or child outcomes, and included at least 10 participants. Here we used IPD data shared by March 2022 from 18 studies from international health organisations and research networks, comprising 24 unique datasets, in 11 countries. Datasets were harmonised with standardised definitions, using variables related to pregnant individuals, methods used for ZIKV diagnoses, fetal characteristics and outcomes, and pooled for analysis. Frequentist and Bayesian regression methods were applied to estimate outcome prevalence and evaluate the association between maternal ZIKV infection and fetal loss, microcephaly and congenital zika syndrome as primary outcomes.

Findings Data including 9568 pregnant individuals and 9608 newborns, were harmonised. The risk of severe primary microcephaly was significantly higher in ZIKV-positive pregnancies (1.5%, CI 0.8%–2.7%) compared to ZIKV-negative ones (0.3%, CI 0.1%–1.0%), with a relative risk of 4.5 (CI 1.5–13.3) in the one-stage meta-analysis. While some risk estimates were consistent between Bayesian and Frequentist methods, estimates for other outcomes varied, underscoring the influence of both the analytical approach and the definition of ZIKV on the associations.

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CRFs = Accelerated, Interoperable Evidence Generation

World Health Organization ISARIC PARTICIPANT IDENTIFICATION #: [][][][][][]-[][][][][][][]

MODULE 1: PRESENTATION/ADMISSION CASE REPORT FORM

CLINICAL INCLUSION CRITERIA

Suspected or confirmed novel coronavirus (COVID-19) infection: YES NO

Is COVID-19 the reason for hospital admission?

Yes, COVID-19 is the reason for hospital admission

No, the patient is admitted to hospital for a reason other than COVID-19

DEMOGRAPHICS

Clinical centre name: _____ Country: _____

Enrolment date /first COVID-19 assessment date: [_] [_] [_] / [_] [_] [_] / [2] [0] [_] [_]

Ethnic group (check all that apply): Arab Black East Asian South Asian West Asian Latin American White Aboriginal/First Nations Other: _____ Unknown

Employed as a Healthcare Worker? YES NO Unknown Employed in a microbiology laboratory? YES NO Unknown

Sex at Birth: Male Female Not specified/Unknown Age [_] [_] [_] years OR [_] [_] months

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Respiratory Medicine
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Articles

Clinical course and outcomes of critically ill patients with SARS-CoV-2 pneumonia in Wuhan, China: a single-centered, retrospective, observational study

Xiaobo Yang MD ^{a, b, d, †}, Yuan Yu MD ^{a, b, †}, Jiqian Xu MD ^{a, b, †}, Prof Huaqing Shu MD ^{a, b, †}, Prof Jia'an Xia MD ^{d, †}, Prof Hong Liu MD ^{a, b, d, †}, Yongran Wu MD ^{a, b}, Lu Zhang MD ^b, Prof Zhui Yu MD ^f, Prof Minghao Fang MD ^c, Prof Ting Yu MD ^d, Yaxin Wang MD ^{a, b}, Shangwen Pan MD ^{a, b}, Prof Xiaojing Zou MD ^{a, b}, Prof Shiyong Yuan MD ^{a, b}, Prof You Shang MD ^{a, b, d, †}

Features of 20 133 UK patients in hospital with covid-19 using the ISARIC WHO Clinical Characterisation Protocol: prospective observational cohort study

Annemarie B Docherty,^{1,2} Ewen M Harrison,¹ Christopher A Green,³ Hayley E Hardwick,^{4,5} Riinu Pius,¹ Lisa Norman,¹ Karl A Holden,⁶ Jonathan M Read,⁷ Frank Dondelinger,⁷ Gail Carson,⁸

ARTICLES | VOLUME 20, ISSUE 6, P697-706, JUNE 01, 2020 PDF [1 MB]

Clinical and virological data of the first cases of COVID-19 in Europe: a case series

Prof Francois-Xavier Lescure, MD [†], Prof Lila Bouadma, MD [†], Duc Nguyen, MD, Marion Parisey, MD, Paul-Henri Wicky, MD, Sylvie Behillil, PharmD et al. Show all authors Show footnotes

ARTICLES | VOLUME 395, ISSUE 10239, P1763-1770, JUNE 06, 2020 PDF [351 KB]

Epidemiology, clinical course, and outcomes of critically ill adults with COVID-19 in New York City: a prospective cohort study

Matthew J Cummings, MD, Matthew R Baldwin, MD, Darryl Abrams, MD, Samuel D Jacobson, BA, Benjamin J Meyer, BA, Elizabeth M Balough, MPhil et al. Show all authors

FAIR Data = Actionable Evidence

Slide from Laura Merson

~1 million patient records
83 countries
1886 health care facilities

>130 manuscripts
19 clinical reports
4 dashboards

Objective: Create a web-based tool for rapid generation of e-CRFs - 'CRF Builder'

Deliverable: Modular eCRFs web interface

Cooperation with ISARIC (International Severe Acute Respiratory Infections Consortium)'s tool: **BRIDGE**.

<https://bridge.isaric.org/>

Cooperation focus

Subtask 1: Multi-language adaptability, automated and validated Translation process

Subtask 2: Variable Manager

CoMeCT Task 4.2 Transform generic eCRFs from CDISC into OMOP-CDM to support analyses across trials & cohorts

Scalable, secure and cost-effective architecture to support harmonisation to OMOP CDM & reuse within OHDSI for EU-wide, multicentre, prospective IDPP and AMR cross-cohort studies & linkages to RWD (e.g., DARWIN EU)

Central Database

Basic research consented for data sharing

Aggregate data globally

Download, analyze locally

Secure Cloud

Large scale research datasets

Aggregate data globally

Analyze centrally in secure cloud

Federated Approach

Connecting national genomics initiatives

Host data locally

Analyze data remotely and collate results

User

Data transmission

Data Visiting

Results sent back to user

How can federated reuse of participant-level data help us in EID detection/response?

Federated reuse of participant-level data for EID detection/response

Data providers (e.g. hospitals, biobanks) preserve control, security, accountability

Reuse dataset in real-time, vs sending static dataset

Do not have to move big data (e.g. imaging data, genomic data) or deal with cold chain as for samples

Privacy-by-design approach can reduce legal and ethical barriers to data and sample reuse

Facilitates enabling individual rights in data (e.g., GDPR right to erasure)

(In theory) enables real-time cross-national analysis in the research response to emerging pathogens

Standardised Health Data & Data Meshes for Federated EID Detection & Response

Emerging pathogens don't respect borders—data & data commons must connect.

TREs won't work, we need real-time federated reuse of existing data flows.

Users need FAIR (meta)data for data capture, exchange, provenance, access/permissions and interoperable infrastructures for federated data reuse.

Linked data unlocks value for pandemic forecasting, research, and care.

Trust requires benefits for data providers & FAIR provenance (meta)data, machine-actionable access conditions/permissions

Need for cross-domain data to identify & contextualise health data

Reuse of RWD becomes more critical for public health emergencies and addressing health challenges for MCH & other vulnerable populations

RDA/CODATA working group on health data commons

What investments are needed to enable the federated reuse of participant-level data across health data commons for epidemic detection & response?

What investments are needed to enable cross-domain data reuse for One Health and EID detection & response?

WORKING GROUP

Health Data Commons GORC Profile WG

Group Stage: Getting Started

Share

+ Join Group

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/health-data-commons-gorc-profile-wg/activity/>

3 key points

1. Investments in data should produce immediate, visible benefits to individuals, providers, health facilities, and health systems during and outside of pandemics. Benefits should be directed at data producers to support their investment in quality data and in data reuse.

2. Federated reuse of interoperable, high-quality participant-level data would work much better for pandemics than sharing data.

3. FAIR data (data interoperability) is not the endpoint.

What is the endpoint?

Interoperability is NOT the endpoint

Data reuse is also not the endpoint

Is data reuse building better surveillance, clinical care, R&D?

If not, why not?

**We need living metadata & actionable metrics at every level of the funding
→ data reuse → impact lifecycle**

Acknowledgements

ecraid

Base

CoMeCT

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